

Spectrophotometric Determination of Niobium(V) with Catechol and 1, 2-Diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic Acid

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Manuscript received 14 June 1976, revised 7 January 1977, accepted 23 August 1977

Niobium(V) reacts with catechol in aqueous solutions in presence of 1, 2-Diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic acid (DCTA) forming an orange red coloured complex with an absorption maximum at 470 nm around pH 3.8 in tartrate medium. The system conforms to Beer's law for an optimum range (for $\frac{1}{4}$ " path length) 0.65-9.66 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of niobium. The behaviour of many cations and anions and also synthetic mixture corresponding to the composition of samarskite mineral were studied for their interference in the determination of niobium.

METHODS for the determination of niobium are generally long and tedious, and require preliminary separation of interfering ions. Masking agents, added to improve selectivity, greatly reduce the sensitivity of many methods. Mixed ligand complexes of niobium and tantalum were studied for their stoichiometry, stability constants^{1,2} and analytical determinations³⁻⁶. Catechol complex of niobium in the presence of DCTA was studied in tartrate medium. Optimum conditions for its analytical determinations were established. Many cations and anions do not interfere in the estimation of niobium and their tolerance limits were also found out and described in this paper.

Experimental

Reagents and equipment: Known weights of specpure (Johnson Mathey and Co) oxides of niobium (0.0266 gm/100 ml) was fused with 1 gm potassium bisulphate and taken in 0.75% tartaric acid.

D.C.T.A. A solution of DCTA (Aldrich Chemical Co) 0.01M was prepared in 0.004M sodium hydroxide.

Catechol: Freshly prepared aqueous solution of catechol (0.05M) recrystallised pure sample (Riedel, W. Germany) was used.

0.75% aqueous solution of tartaric acid (AR), titanium and tantalum in 0.75% of tartaric acid solution (AR) and aqueous solutions of all other foreign ions were used.

A Bausch & Lomb 'Spectronic 20' Spectrophotometer using $1/2$ " matched cells and a 'Systronics (India) pH meter (Type 322-1) were used.

Procedure

11 ml of catechol, 6 ml of DCTA and varying amounts of niobium in tartrate medium were mixed

and the pH was adjusted at 3.8 ± 0.1 and made up to 25 ml with distilled water of the same pH. The final tartrate concentration was maintained with 1-2 ml of tartaric acid solution including the niobium (tartrate medium) concentration taken. Absorbance measurements can be taken at 470 nm, 8 hours after preparation of the solutions at room temperature (25°).

Results

Niobium(V) in tartrate medium reacts with catechol having no absorption in the visible range but by adding DCTA it forms an orange-red coloured complex with absorption maximum at 470 nm. This colour formation in tartrate medium was utilised for the analytical determination of niobium, after establishing the optimum conditions.

Time and Temperature Study

The formation of niobium complex with catechol and DCTA was slow and completes in 8 hours and remains stable up to 4 days at room temperature. However at higher temperatures the colour intensity decreases probably due to dissociation.

pH Variation

The spectra of the complex in the visible region at different pH indicated that absorption maximum at 470 nm persists only in a narrow pH region, 3.7 to 4.1. Further work was carried out at pH 3.8 ± 0.1 .

Effects of Reagent Concentration: Catechol Variation

The effect of catechol variation on colour intensity with 1 ml of metal, 3 ml of DCTA and varying concentrations of catechol solutions at pH 3.8 ± 0.1 in total volume of 25 ml indicated that colour saturation was obtained with 11 ml of catechol. Further increase of catechol concentration up to 14 ml indicated no significant change in absorbance values for the above conditions of study.

DCTA Variation

The effect of DCTA on colour formation indicated that colour intensity increases with increasing concentration of DCTA and attains a steady value around 6 ml and remains constant in a region of 5 to 8 ml conc. in total vol. of 25 ml.

Tartaric Acid Variation

For the above system of 1 ml niobium, 6 ml DCTA, 11 ml catechol solutions in 25 ml, the intensity of absorption remained constant in the region of 0.3 ml of tartaric acid in excess of 2 ml of niobium solution in tartrate medium already taken.

Beer's Law Range, Sensitivity

The optimum niobium conc. range for its estimation and measurement at 470 nm using $\frac{1}{2}$ " matched cells was found to be 0.65-9.66 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of niobium and conformity to Beer's law was obtained. Sensitivity of the estimation is 0.013 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of niobium for $A=0.001$ absorbance unit and 1.0 cm path length.

Study of Foreign ions

The following foreign ions did not show significant interference in the estimation of 92.96 μg of niobium in 25 ml by the recommended procedure.

W ⁶⁺ (183 μg);	Ta ⁵⁺ (92.96 μg);	Ti ⁴⁺ (46 μg)
Th ⁴⁺ (2320 μg);	Zr ⁴⁺ (730 μg);	Cr ³⁺ (104 μg)
Al ³⁺ (235 μg);	Sb ³⁺ (121.76 μg);	Y ³⁺ (889 μg)
Fe ³⁺ (111.70 μg);	Sn ²⁺ (593 μg);	Hg ²⁺ (4012 μg)
Be ²⁺ (92.96 μg);	Pb ²⁺ (2072 μg);	Ca ²⁺ (200 μg)
Cu ²⁺ (127 μg);	Na ⁺ (4000 μg);	K ⁺ (4000 μg)
NH ₄ ⁺ (1000 μg);	PO ₄ ³⁻ (2850 μg);	SO ₄ ²⁻ (2850 μg)
NO ₃ ⁻ (2840 μg);	Cl ⁻ (2000 μg);	

However at lower concentrations Mo⁶⁺, F⁻, (COO)²⁻ are interfering seriously.

Seven synthetic mixtures corresponding to the composition of Samerskite mineral were estimated with a relative standard deviation of 1%

Nb ₂ O ₅ (44.54%);	Ta ₂ O ₅ (8.05%);	TiO ₂ (1.62%);
SiO ₂ (0.22%);	SnO ₂ (1.48%);	Fe ₂ O ₃ (14.77%);
CaO (0.94%);	MgO (0.03%);	Al ₂ O ₃ (0.79%);
ThO ₂ (1.21%);	Ce ₂ O ₃ (0.8%);	Y ₂ O ₃ (13.93%);
MnO (1.60%);	PbO (2.04%);	UO ₂ ²⁺ (6.03%);
Na ₂ O (0.21%);	K ₂ O (0.21%);	Na ₂ O (0.29%).

Estimation of niobium by this method will be useful for the analysis of minerals or alloys.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.S.R.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (New Delhi) for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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